

Tokopedia Innovation Through Promotion and Easy to Use Applications on Community Buying Interest in the Pandemic Time Covid 19

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ABSTRACT : Promotion and ease of using applications (user friendly) from Tokopedia fostered public interest in visiting applications and buying products during the Covid 19 Pandemic. The uncertain Covid 19 pandemic has prompted Tokopedia to innovate through promotions and ease of use of applications. The research method used in this research is quantitative method with a sample of 100 respondents to the Tokopedia application users. The results show that there is an influence of Tokopedia's innovation through promotion and ease of use of the application so that people are interested and interested in shopping at Tokopedia during the Covid 19 pandemic. Innovation through continuous promotion can influence people to shop. The prolonged Covid19 pandemic has made people refrain from doing activities outside the home and Tokopedia sees this opportunity. The ease of using the application also influences the public to shop on Tokopedia. The easier it is for people to access the application, it makes them reluctant to switch to other applications.

KEYWORDS : Innovation, Promotion, User friendly, Tokopedia application, Purchase interest

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of Information and Communication Technology is growing rapidly. The industrial revolution 4.0 marks the rapid development of ICT and its use in society. The rapid development of the internet has a significant influence on human life. With the internet, various kinds of information can be obtained easily. The use of the internet is not only used to obtain and provide information but can also be used as a means of conducting trade transactions which are commonly known as electronic commerce or e-commerce.

The development of e-commerce in Indonesia is developing quite well. Kominfo noted that in 2014-2016 Indonesia was in the 6th position for internet users. In 2017-2018 Indonesia is in the 5th position. Above Indonesia, currently the top five internet user countries in the world are occupied by China, the United States, India, Brazil, and Japan. The number of internet users in China is currently recorded at 643 million, more than double the netter population in China. United States of America 252 million.

Statistical data shows that Indonesia is included in the 10 countries with the largest internet users in the world. Indonesia is in fifth place with 143.26 million internet users as of March 2019. This figure has a slight difference of 5.8 million with Brazil, which has 149.06 million internet users.

The top ranking was obtained by China with 829 million internet users. The second rank is quite far from China, up to 269 million, namely India with 560 million internet users. The United States (US) followed with 292.89 million internet users.

Referring to research conducted by Rendy and Rizal (2017) promotion has a positive and significant effect on trust. In this study, it is shown that re-testing of promotion factors is proven to affect trust through the frequency of promotions, quality of promotions, quantity of promotions, and time of promotions. This research was conducted by continuing the suggestions for the development of a research model from Jiang et al. (2014) which states that promotion has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. In this study, it is shown that re-testing of promotional factors is proven to influence consumer purchase interest.

Among the many e-commerce services in Indonesia, Tokopedia is one that is quite popular in the community. iPrice Group named Tokopedia as the e-commerce with the largest number of monthly web visitors in the third quarter of 2019. Tokopedia's total monthly web visitors were 66 million visitors. The next rank is filled by Shopee with 56 million visitors and Bukalapak with 43 million monthly web visitors. iPrice Group is a meta-search site that conducts research on shopping behavior. The data used is using the average website visitors sourced from SimilarWeb.

The problem that is the basis of this research is the high competition with other e-commerce such as Shopee and Bukalapak. In addition, there are still some users who have difficulty understanding the use and how to transact on Tokopedia.

In Fitri Dwi Rahawati and Mahendra Adhi Nugroho's research with the title Pengaruh the quality of information, use, and ease of use on the interest in using E-Commerce Tokobagus.com, it was concluded that the quality of information, usability, and convenience simultaneously had a positive and significant effect on the interest in using E-Commerce Tokobagus.com.

In the journal Widya Sastika (2016) with the title analysis of the effect of website quality (webqual 4.0) on purchasing decisions on the E-Commerce website Traveloka (case study: Traveloka users in Bandung in 2015) has the effect of variable X, namely website quality using the webquai method. 4.0 towards variable Y, namely the purchase decision on the Traveloka e-commerce website, is significant.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

According to Dwi Rahmawati (2013), in her research journal e-commerce is described as the process of buying and selling goods or services on the world wide web internet or the process of buying and selling or exchanging products, services and information through information networks including the internet. Meanwhile, according to Widya Sastika (Chaffey and Smith 2008: 13), "Emarketing is online marketing whether via web sites, online ads, opt-in email, interactive kiosk, interactive TV or mobiles". What that means, Emarketing is online marketing whether through websites, online advertisements, opt-in e-mails, interactive kiosks, interactive TVs or cell phones. E-marketing brings you closer to customers, can understand them better and maintains a dialogue with them too. E-marketing is broader than e-commerce which is only limited to transactions between organizations and people who have an interest. Meanwhile, e-marketing includes the entire process which includes marketing.

In the journal Arief Adi Satria (Kotler, 2010: 173), argues that sales promotion is a short-term incentive to encourage the purchase or sale of a product or service. Meanwhile, according to William J Stanton promotion is advertising, personal selling and other ways of selling sales promotion purposes. According to the book written by Kotler (2010: 174), it explains that promotion aims to attract consumers to try new products, lure consumers to leave competing products, or to make consumers leave ripe products, or hold or give awards to consumers who loyal.

In the journal Iyad A (Ross, 2001) he defines promotion mix as "the total marketing communication program of a particular product". (Adebisi, 2006) defines promotion mix as "any marketing effort whose function is to inform current or potential consumers about the benefits of a product with the aim of persuading consumers to start buying or continue to buy the company's products or services". Promotion mix refers to describing a set of organizational tools that can be adopted to effectively communicate the benefits of its products to its consumers ensuring that the organization's promotional strategy is well received and accepted by its consumers, the organization must have a strong way of communication because good communication skills and effective promotion are tools for every organization to compete in the industry.

According to De Pelsmacker et al., (2001) personal selling can be defined as a face-to-face communication tool used to inform and establish long-term relationships with prospective customers. Kotler (2000) notes that personal selling is a useful tool for communicating with current and potential buyers. Personal selling involves a two-way flow of communication between buyers and sellers that is designed to influence consumer purchasing decisions. Furthermore, according to Fill, (2006) the main feature of personal selling is the

effect it has, meaning that salespeople are more likely to break through, get consumer attention and even be remembered later. Salespeople have the opportunity to tailor the message to the type of customer they are dealing with. Due to two-way communication, there is less danger of misunderstanding as salespeople can get immediate, on-the-spot feedback. Weitz et al., (2004) noted that an important role of salespeople is to engage and collect information related to potential customers, adjust sales strategies based on that information, carry messages that implement organizational strategies, evaluate the effect of messages and make adjustments to this evaluation.

The consumer purchasing decision process is a series of stages made by customers when and after buying a product, Pride and Ferrell (2012) note that to understand customer purchasing decisions, marketers must understand the consumption process and product use in customer perceptions. The consumer purchasing decision goes through five general steps as follows: The first stage in the purchase decision is the need / problem recognition, it is an important and important thing.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (Business Communication 2008), advertising (advertising) is a form of communication by marketers to inform and persuade the market and target market. With low costs, advertising can reach many buyers who are scattered in various right (target markets). With good advertising, it also creates good trust from the public towards companies that carry out advertising activities. With the advertising activity, message recipients can compare with other advertisements, or compare with advertisements that have been installed by other competitors. Advertising itself has an open nature, and consumers tend to see the advertised product as the standard of the company that carries out the ad. The big advertisement itself says that regarding the sales size, popularity and success of the company. Rendra Widyatama in his book entitled "Introduction to Advertising," states that of all the terms regarding advertising basically have the same 6 principles. Of the six principles I have broken down into five main elements, namely: Suryadi, Didik (2011: 62)

Direct Marketing (Direct Marketing) is a form of direct promotion by way of marketing products or goods in order to get a reaction directly from consumers. Direct marketing does not mean having to be face to face but rather marketing aimed directly at certain consumers. Direct marketing can also use telephone, email, or other media that can be used to offer sales of these products. In this way, customers will definitely react to it.

Technology that is easy to understand will affect a person's perception that the technology is easy to use. In the case of e-commerce use, convenience arises if consumers can access various sites and buy the necessary products without having to go to the store because the goods are sent via postal services. Information technology users believe that information technology is more flexible, easy to understand and easy to operate (compatible) as characteristics of ease of use. Davis (1989) provides several indicators of the ease of use of information technology, including computers that are very easy to learn, computers do easily what users want, increased user skills by using computers and computers are very easy to operate.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, the research paradigm used is the positivism paradigm. According to Ardianto (2009), the positivism paradigm views communication as a linear process that reflects an attempt by the sender to influence or change the knowledge of the message recipient. The communication process that occurs is determined by the sender of the message (source-oriented). The success of the communication process depends on the efforts made by the sender of the message in packaging and attracting the attention of the message recipient.

Dwi Saputro (2013) This type of research is an associative quantitative study with the unit of analysis being the customers who use internet banking services at Bank Mandiri. Associative quantitative research is research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables.

This research uses explanatory research method. According to Singarimbun and Efendi (2006: 5), explanatory research is, "Research that explains the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing". The purpose of this study is to explain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable either jointly or individually based on the test results.

In the Adilang Journal, Oroh, Moniharapon (Sugiyono, 2010: 120). Population is a generalization area consisting of objects / subjects that have certain qualities or characteristics that are determined by the researcher to be studied and then draw conclusions. Population is not just people, but objects and other natural objects. Population is also not just the number that is in the object or subject being studied, but includes all the characteristics / properties possessed by the subject or object. The population used is the Bekasi City community with a total of 2,943,859 individuals (bps.go.id, 2018) who have made purchase transactions through online media.

The sample used in this study is purposive sampling, where the authors collect samples who have done transactions on Tokopedia at least once. In the journal Widiyanti, Prasilowati (2015) the sampling technique used was to combine purposive sampling and convenience sampling. Purposive sampling criteria are individuals who have done online shopping transactions for their own consumption / use once a year. The questionnaire is designed to filter respondents by requiring that they have transacted at least once. The number of samples is determined using the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n: Number of samples

N: Total population

e: Error tolerance

1: Constant number

From the formula above, the population of Bekasi City is 2,943,859 people with the Margin of Error determined, which is the maximum tolerable error rate of 10% and the confidence level of 90%.

According to Arikunto (2007), in general, research subjects are things, objects, or people used in a study. The subjects in this study were all people in Bekasi City, which in 2018 according to BPS data, the population of Bekasi City was 2,943,859 individuals.

According to Sugiyono (2009), the object of research is the nature or value of people or activities that have certain variations that have been determined by researchers to be studied and then draw conclusions. As for the objects of this study, namely three variables, namely the variable promotion, ease of use, and purchase interest.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tokopedia is an online-based shopping mall that allows every person and business owner in Indonesia to open and manage their online store easily and free of cost, while providing a safe and comfortable online buying and selling experience. Using Tokopedia is very easy and free of charge. Tokopedia actually does not have a branch company, it only has a head office located in Jakarta.

When Tokopedia arrived on the market on August 17, 2009, Tokopedia was founded by Wiliam Tanuwijaya and Leontinus Alpha Edison. Tokopedia received seed funding from PT Dwitama in 2009. Then it got a very large capital of around USD 100 million or IDR 1.2 trillion which was injected several months by Softbank Internet and Media Inc. and Sequoia Capital.

So far, Tokopedia has received many awards, including: Marketeers of the Year 2014 for the e-commerce sector at the Markplus Conference 2015 event held by Markplus Inc on December 11, 2014. And on May 12, 2016, Tokopedia was again chosen as the Best Company in Consumer Industry from the 2016 Indonesia Digital Economy Award.

Respondent Identity Based on Gender

Following are the characteristics of respondents divided by gender, divided into 2. Namely, respondents are male and female.

Table 4.1 Characteristics of Respondents by Gender

No.	Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Woman	75	75%
2.	Men	20	20%
Total		100	100%

Identity of Respondents by Age

Following are the characteristics of respondents divided by age divided into 4. Namely respondents who have ages 16-20 years, 21-30 years, 31-40 years, > 40 years.

Table 4.2 Characteristics of Respondents by Age

No.	Age	Total Responden	Percentage (%)
1.	16-20	29	29%
2.	21-30	48	48%
3.	31-40	10	10%
4.	> 40	13	13%
Total		100	100%

Based on the results of the table above, it can be seen that respondents aged 16-20 years are 29 people (29%), respondents aged 21-30 years are 48 people (48%), respondents aged 31-40 years are 10 people (10%), and respondents who are more than 40 years old are 13 people (11%). So in 100 samples it can be seen based on the age of the most respondents aged 21-30 years as many as 48 people (48%).

Respondent Identity Based on Occupation

The following are the characteristics of the respondents which are divided based on occupation which are divided into 5. Namely respondents who work as students / students, civil servants, private employees, teachers / lecturers, entrepreneurs.

Table 4.3 Characteristics of Respondents by Occupation

No.	Profession	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Student	28	28%
2.	Lecturer	4	4%
3.	Government Employees	7	7%
4.	Private Employees	39	39%
5.	Entrepreneur	22	22%
Total		100	100%

Based on the results of the table above, it can be seen that respondents who have jobs as Students / Students are 28 people (28%), respondents who have jobs as Teachers / Lecturers are 4 people (4%), respondents who have jobs as Civil Servants are 7 people (7%), respondents who have private employee jobs

are 39 people (39%), and respondents who have entrepreneurial jobs are 22 people (22%) So in 100 samples it can be seen that based on the work of the most respondents are as private employees as many as 39 people (39%) .

Validity Test

In the use of the validity test, the researcher used SSS version 16.0. Then the results will be compared with the r-table value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with the degrees of freedom determined by $dk = n-2$, then the r-table will be obtained. For the items of each question will be calculated based on correlation ($r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$) then the question is considered valid. The number of respondents used is 100 respondents, then the r table value can be calculated:

$$dk = n - 2 = 100 - 2 = 98$$

Reliability Test

In measuring the reliability test, it can be measured by the level of measurement results if it is repeated. Whether or not data can be seen from the resulting Cronbach alpha coefficient, a number that is close to 1 (one) can be said to have reliability. A data is said to be accurate if the Cronbach alpha coefficient value is greater than 0.60. In this test the author uses the SPSS version 16.0 program.

Normality Test

The purpose of the normality assumption test is to test whether in a regression model, the independent and dependent variables have a normal or near normal distribution. This test uses the Normal P-P of Regression Standardized Residual graph approach. The basis for decision making is if the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the diagonal line, it fulfills the assumption of normality. Below are the results of the Normality Test.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Picture 4.1.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variants from one residual of one observation to another. One way to approach heteroscedasticity is to look at

the scatter plot graph between the predicted value of the dependent variable (ZPRED) and its residual (SRESID). If there are dots forming a certain regular pattern such as wavy, widened, then narrowed, heteroscedasticity has occurred. If the dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis without forming a specific pattern, there is no heteroscedasticity. To detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity, it can be done by looking at the presence or absence of a certain pattern on the plot graph. Following below are the results of the Heteroscedasticity Test.

Scatterplot

Picture 4.2.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether the regression model finds a correlation between the independent variables (Ghozali, 2006). One method for diagnosing multicollinearity is measuring the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF). The tolerance value is to measure the variability of the selected independent variable that is not explained by other independent variables. The calculation results show that there are no independent variables that have a tolerance value less than 10%. The calculation of the VIF value also shows that there are no independent variables that have a VIF value of more than 10. So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Correlation Analysis Results

Based on the results of SPSS version 16.0 from the table above, it can be seen that the correlation value is 0.822. If the correlation coefficient > 0.5 , it is strong. Because the correlation value is $0.822 > 0.5$. It can be concluded that the influence of the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) has a strong relationship.

T Test (Partial Test)

This test is used to determine whether the regression model the independent variable (X) has a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y). The use of this T test is to test whether the promotional variable (X1) and the ease of use of the Tokopedia application (X2) partially affect the buying interest (Y) of the people in Bekasi city.

The criteria in this test if the significant level is < 0.05 , then there is an effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. (H_0 is rejected, H_a is accepted) If the significant level is > 0.05 , then there is no effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. (H_0 accepted H_a rejected).

Discussion

1. Based on the results of the calculations that have been done, it can be seen that the promotion variable has an influence on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi.
2. For the variable ease of use of the Tokopedia application, it has an influence on asking people to buy in Bekasi city.
3. For promotion variables and ease of use of the Tokopedia application, it has an influence on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted regarding the effect of promotion and ease of use of the Tokopedia application on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi, several conclusions can be drawn that answer the following research questions:

1. The promotion variable has an influence on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi. This can be seen from the results of the T test calculation, where T is greater than T table, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted (there is an influence between promotion on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi).
2. The variable ease of use of the application has an influence on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi. This can be seen from the results of the T test calculation, where T count is greater than T table, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted (there is an influence between the ease of using the Tokopedia application on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi).
3. Promotion variables and ease of use of the Tokopedia application have an influence on people's buying interest in the city of Bekasi. This can be seen from the results of the F Test calculation, where F count is greater than F table, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted (there is a significant influence together between the independent variables, namely promotion and ease of use of the Tokopedia application on the dependent variable of interest. buy the people in the city of Bekasi together (simultaneously)).

VI. Acknowledgements

This research has limitations, so below are some things that can be suggested for improvement. Good academic advice and practical advice.

1. As academic advice for further researchers, it is hoped that it can expand the research sample to see the overall and varied range of influence between variables. Then provide a deeper discussion of other factors that affect the dependent variable apart from the independent variables of this study.
2. As practical advice for Tokopedia application companies to be able to use this research as a guide in designing the right strategy to improve promotion and ease of use of the Tokopedia application. Ease of use of the application is a dominant factor in this research, it is hoped that Tokopedia can consider always improving services in terms of ease of use.

REFERENCES

Journal Papers:

- [1] Cheung, Christy. M.K dan Matthew K.L. Lee, 2012, "What Drives Consumers to Spread Electronic Word of Mouth in Online Consumer Opinion Platform" Decision Support System 53, 218-225, Hongkong.
- [2] Davis, Fred D, 1989, "Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease Of Use, And User Acceptance Of Information Technology", Mis Quarterly, hal 319- 340.
- [3] Khanfar, I, A, 2016, "The Effect Of Promotion Mix Elements On Consumers Buying Decisions Of Mobile Service: The Case Of Umniah Telecommunication Company At Zarqa City- Jordan", *European Journal Of Business And Management*, 8 (5).
- [4] Kotler, P, 2000, "Marketing Management , Millenium Edition". *Marketing Management*, 23(6), hal 188–193.
- [5] Martono, M., and S. R Iriani. 2014. "Analysis of the Influence of Product Quality, Price and Promotion on Consumer Purchase Intention of Batik Products in Sendang Duwur Lamongan", *Journal of Management Science*, 2 (2), pp. 687-699.

- [6] Maulana, Rendi, and Kurniawati, Kezia, "The Effect of E-Service Quality on Consumer Purchase Intention (Case Study on the Korean Denim Website)", *Management Journal*, 13 (2).
- [7] Nugrahani, S, D, 2011, "E-Commerce for Small and Medium Business Product Marketing", *Journal of Management and Business Segments*, No. 1.
- [8] Pratama, R, B, and Magnadi, R, H, "Analysis of the Influence of Promotion and Security Perceptions on Trust and Its Implications for Purchasing Intention in E-Commerce (Studies on Blibli.Com Users)", *Diponegoro Journal Of Management*, 6 (3) , Pp. 1-11.
- [9] Priansa, D, J, 2016. "The effect of E-WOM and perceived value on consumer decisions to shop online at Lazada", *Ecodemica*, 4 (1), 2016.
- [10] Priyanti, Yuli, Susanti, Febsri, and Azizz Nazaruddin, 2017, "87 Consumer Purchase Interests of Bata Shoe Stores in Raya Raya Padang Judging from Attitudes and Ads", *Pundi Journal*, 1 (2).
- [11] Rahmawati, Fitri D, Dan Nugroho M. A., 2013, "The Influence of Information Quality, Usefulness, and Ease of Use on Interest in Using E-Commerce Tokobagus.Com", *Profit Journal*, Pages 28-53.
- [12] Sanjaya, Suya, 2015, "The Influence of Promotions and Brands on Purchasing Decisions at Pt. Sinar Sosro Medan ", *Management and Business Scientific Journal*, 16 (02).
- [13] Saputro, B, D, and Sukirno, "The Effect of Perceptions of Ease of Use, Trust, Computer Anxiety and Service Quality on Interests in Using Internet Banking", *Nominal Journal*, 2 (1).
- [14] Sastika, Widya, 2016, "Analysis of the Effect of Website Quality (Webqual 4.0) on Purchasing Decisions on Traveloka E-Commerce Website (Case Study: Traveloka Users in Bandung City in 2015)", 2016 National Seminar on Information and Communication Technology (Sentika 2016), pages 18-19.
- [15] Satria, A, A, 2017, "The Effect of Price, Promotion, and Product Quality on Consumer Purchase Intention at Company A-36", *Journal of Management and Business Start-Up*, 2 (1).
- [16] Tjahjono, Amelia, Dkk, 2103, "Marketing Mix Analysis, Social Environment, Psychology of Online Purchasing Decisions for Women's Clothing", *Petra Marketing Management Journal*, 1 (2), pp. 1 -9.
- [17] Widiyanto, Ibnu, 2015. "Purchasing Behavior Through the Internet". 17 (2), pp. 109 - 112.

Books:

- [18] Armstrong, Gerry Dan Kotler, Philip, 2008. *Principles of Marketing, Volume I, Twelfth Edition*. Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [19] Chaffey, D & Smith, Pr, 2008. *E-Marketing : Excellence*, Butterworthheinemann, Uk.
- [20] Ghozali, Imam, 2006. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with Spss, 4th Edition*, Undip Publisher Agency, Semarang.
- [21] Goldsmith, R, 2008. *Electronic Word-of-Mouth: E-commerce*, Idea Group Reference Global, Florida.
- [22] Kalakota Dan Whinston, 1996. *Frontiers Of Electronic Commerce*, Addison-Wesley PublilshingCompany, Inc, Massachusetts.
- [23] Kaplan, Andreas. M. dan Haenlein, Michael, 2010. *Users of the World, Unite! The Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media*, Business Horizon.
- [24] Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G, 2010. *Principles Of Marketing*, Thirteen Edition, Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- [25] Ross T, 2001. *Marketing As A Concept*, Practice Hall Press, New York.